

athena
gender equality to unlock
research potential

D3.2 Programme and material of the Gender Training Programme

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Grant Agreement n°: 101006416

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

info@athenaequality.eu
www.athenaequality.eu

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Version history

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	15.07.22	Draft version sent to the project consortium and the Steering Committee for review	Cira Mendoza, Michelle Perello
1.0	26.07.22	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the consortium and the Steering Committee	Project consortium / Steering Committee

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP3
Task	T3.3
Deliverable	D3.2 Programme and material of the Gender Training Programme
Due Date	31/07/2022
Submission Date	29/07/2022
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	PP1 – Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation (CE)
Version	1.0
Status	Final
Author(s)	Cira Mendoza, Michelle Perello
Reviewers	Steering Committee

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Table of Contents

List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures.....	4
Acronyms and Abbreviations	4
1. Introduction.....	5
1.1 Purpose and scope	5
1.2 Document structure.....	5
2. The Gender Training Programme	5
2.1 Objective of the training programme	6
2.2 Structure of the training programme	6
2.3 Preparation of the training programme	9
3. ATHENA Gender Training Programmes.....	9
3.1 JSI training programme	12
3.2 UJK training programme	17
3.3 UB training programme	22
3.4 ULPGC training programme.....	26
3.5 UVSK SAV training programme	31
3.6 URAK training programme	34
3.7 FRCT training programme.....	38
4. Material of the Gender Training Programme	42

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

List of Tables

Table 1. Structure and main characteristics of the gender training programme	6
Table 2. Non-exhaustive list of potential topics and objectives for the gender training programme.....	7
Table 3. Topics and modules of each ATHENA training programme	10
Table 4. Schedule of the ATHENA training programmes.....	11

List of Figures

Figure 1. How to access the material at the ATHENA e-platform.....	42
--	----

Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACIISI	Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información
CE	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L.
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
FRCT	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)
GE	Gender equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI Committees	Gender Equality Plans Implementation Committees
GA	Grant Agreement
JSI	Jozef Stefan Institute
RFO	Research funding organization
RPO	Research performing organization
T	Task
UB	University of Bucharest
UJK	Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce
ULPGC	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
UVSK SAV	Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej
WP	Work package

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable, entitled 'Programme and material of the gender training programme' presents the programme and material of the capacity building activities towards gender equality developed under the ATHENA framework. These activities, undertaken under project work package (WP) 3 'Capacity building activities', are targeted to the whole institutional community of the project partners institutions, i.e. Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organizations (RFOs). Thus, target groups involve researchers, professors, high and middle management, administrative staff, human resources staff as well as students for the case of RPOs.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable describes:

- The objectives and structure of the ATHENA gender training programme and how it was prepared (**section 2**).
- The institutional gender training outlines and agendas for each ATHENA partner organisation (**section 3**).
- Access to the material developed by the ATHENA institutions to implement their gender training programmes (**section 4**).

2. The Gender Training Programme

Training is one of the mandatory requirements set by the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion². This criterion requires that the GEPs include awareness-raising and training actions on gender equality and unconscious bias for staff and decision-making positions. In fact, the ATHENA consortium consider that training actions are key to increase sensitivity to gender equality at the same time as giving people the skills and knowledge to be engaged towards it.

ATHENA RPOs and RFOs implementing GEPs have designed and put in place a gender training programme under T3.2. This training programme addressed the ATHENA GEPI (Gender Equality Plan Implementation) Committees. It was a 'train the trainers' activity, aimed at qualifying the GEPI Committees for them to be able to promote the institutional transformation in terms of gender aspects. As a continuity,

² The Gender Equality Plan (GEP) eligibility criterion of the Horizon Europe Framework for Research and Innovation 2021-2027. Find more information at <https://op.europa.eu/es/publication-detail/-/publication/ffc06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>

the T3.3 foresees the development and implementation of a gender training programme devoted to the whole institutional community. The present document reports on the programme and material of these institutional training programmes.

2.1 Objective of the training programme

The aim of the capacity building is to **create and increase sensitivity of the whole project partner institution to gender equality at the same time as providing with the knowledge and skills to be engaged towards the institutional transformation.**

2.2 Structure of the training programme

Each ATHENA RPO/RFO implementing their GEPs designed a gender training programme under project task T3.3, which is deployed to the whole institutional community, i.e, the internal staff (researchers, professors, administrative staff, human resources (HR) staff) and, for the case of the RPOs, students.

The training programme is composed of at least 5 modules, which focus on different topics and address different groups in accordance with each institution’s needs. Each ATHENA institution has developed the topics and modules of the training programme tailored to the results of the gender diagnostic carried out under WP2. As for the modality, they are delivered both face-to-face and online. The project target is to train at least 150 participants at each project institution.

Table 1 summarises the abovementioned and additional main characteristics of the gender training programme.

Table 1. Structure and main characteristics of the gender training programme

Target group	The whole institution, i.e., institutional staff (and students for the case of RPOs). The training programme should engage the whole organisation, its different levels and roles (The ATHENA target groups (High management; HR professionals; administrative staff; researchers).
Indicator	At least 150 people trained in each ATHENA institution.
Topic	ATHENA institutions determine the specific topics of the programme and its modules based on the results of the assessment carried out under WP2 .
Objective	Specified by each ATHENA institution. The training programme should at least: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cover awareness raising of the whole institution towards gender equality. - Address unconscious bias for staff and decision makers. (These requirements are set in line with the mandatory process-related requirements set by the EC).
Modality	Face-to-face or online.

Format	The training programme may be delivered in different ways, for instance traditional lecture sessions, courses of study or webinars.
Developed by	ATHENA consortium/ ATHENA GEPI Committee members/ Gender experts
Delivered by	ATHENA consortium/ ATHENA GEPI Committee members/ Gender experts
Training programme implementation	From M14 (March 2022) to M22 (November 2022) . The training programme is implemented on an ongoing basis.
Duration of each module	Indicative duration: 2 hours minimum and 10 hours maximum for each module (thus, the total duration of a 5-module training programme is around 10 hours minimum and 50 hours maximum).
Language	English or national languages , based on each ATHENA RPOs/RFOs needs.

As mentioned above, the training programme includes at least 5 modules. Project partners were requested to implement it on an ongoing and long-term basis in accordance with the mandatory process-related requirement set by the EC³. Content-related, the ATHENA institutions were also requested to follow the '*Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans*', which suggests including awareness-raising and training actions on gender equality and unconscious gender bias for staff and decision-makers. Training on unconscious bias are mainly offered in the context of the development of the GEP itself, but it was stressed the importance for it to be incorporated into broader institutional training activities on an ongoing basis. Incorporating it into recruitment or research funding evaluation processes is key to ensuring that unconscious gender bias does not influence decision-making and selection practices.

Indeed, project partners are invited to cover other needed different topics. A non-exhaustive list of potential topics and objectives (see Table 2) was identified and shared with partners to provide them with a first battery of themes. Project partners were invited to adapt the topics and their objectives and/or propose any other/s based on their institutional assessment.

Table 2. Non-exhaustive list of potential topics and objectives for the gender training programme

Topic 1: Unconscious bias (mandatory topic addressing the staff and decision-makers)	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine the arguments that support the value of gender equality and diversity in RPOs/RFOs. Outline the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making. Explore examples and case studies of unconscious bias.
Topic 2: Gender responsive budgeting	

³ Refer to footnote number 2.

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide with skills to improve the processes for planning budgetary strategies and evaluating their design, implementation, results and impact. Provide with the analysis tools to introduce gender mainstreaming in budget programmes, in both their design and implementation, and measure its impact on reducing inequalities. Introduce evaluation as a routine tool of budget management, emphasizing its benefits and offering practical tips on how to use it.
Topic 3: The gender dimension in research	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine how gender considerations are incorporated into research and the importance of these throughout the research process. Introduce participants to gender mainstreaming: Commitment to including gender issues at research in Europe. Examine cases in research where the inclusion of gender issues led to successful outcomes. Explore how the gender dimension can be considered at each phase of the research.
Topic 4: Work-life balance and organizational culture	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the relations between gender equality, organizational culture in research and academic environments and work-life balance. Learn and discuss about inspiring practices for possible interventions and policies.
Topic 5: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the main concepts and concerns regarding gender equality in leadership positions. Understand the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making. Become familiar with tools to improve institutional gender balance in leadership positions and decision-making. Learn about successful implemented measures to improve gender balance on leading positions .
Topic 6: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand and recognize the existing gender imbalances and bias in research organizations in career progression and recruitment. Learning about positive practices to overcome inequalities in recruitment and promotion.
Topic 7: How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the concepts of gender-based violence and sexual harassment and related debates. Raise awareness about the importance of policies to fight gender-based violence. Understand gender-based violence in research institutions and the gender bias that exists within institutional cultures. Learn about practices to improve policies to fight against sexual harassment at work, with focus on RPOs/RFOs.
Topic 8: Tools for an inclusive language	

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Know the main international and national legal and political instruments on equality between men and women.▪ Use inclusive language, either in a gender-neutral way or referring to both sexes.▪ Acquire tools to apply inclusive language.▪ Reflect on misogynistic machismo strategies designed to interfere in women's power of speech, focusing on the concepts: maninterrupting, bropropriating and mansplaining.▪ Practice and reflect on inclusive language application exercises.
------------	---

2.3 Preparation of the training programme

Project partners were provided with guidance to develop and implement their gender training programmes. The guidance document included brief description of the context of the project task; the objective pursued; suggestions for the structure and content of the capacity building; deadlines; important aspects to bear in mind; as well as indications for dissemination and reporting.

Templates for training proposal outline and modules report were also provided for reporting purposes. Section 3 compiles the training outlines for each of the project institutions that are implementing the task and section 4 provides information on the material used/to be used in each of the training programmes.

The individual event reports of this capacity building will be included within the deliverable D3.4 – Reports on learning activities – v2.

3. ATHENA Gender Training Programmes

The Table 3 reports on the topic of each ATHENA training programme as well as each of its specific modules. As it can be seen, all the ATHENA institutions that implement GEPs have planned their gender training programmes under T3.3. The Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society from the regional government of the Canary islands (ACIISI – GOBCAN), organized the training addressed to the whole institutional staff in December 2021. This organization employs a considerably smaller number of employees (around 26 workers) compared to the rest of the project research institutions. Thus, it organized a training programme in which both the GEPI Committee members and the institutional staff participated. Event report of this training may be consulted within project deliverable 'D3.3 – Report on learning activities for GEPI Committees – v1'.

Table 3. Topics and modules of each ATHENA training programme

ATHENA institution	Training topic	Module 1	Module 2	Module 3	Module 4	Module 5	Module 6
JSI	Gender equality at JSI	Unconscious bias	Work-life balance and organizational culture	Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making	Gender equality in career progression and recruitment	Ethics and integrity in research	n/a
UJK	Equal opportunities in science and research	Unconscious bias in the workplace	The gender dimension in research - including gender issues in research	Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in research projects - universal project framework design	Equality in career progression and recruitment	Inclusive language	n/a
UB	A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases	A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases in the University Administration	A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases	A Gender Equal University: useful concepts for students	Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act	Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research	n/a
URAK	Sustainable equality of women and men in the science	Unconscious bias and gender-based violence	Work-life balance and organizational culture.	Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making	Gender equality in career progression and recruitment.	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.	n/a
ULPGC	Advancing towards gender equality at the ULPGC	Leadership and career progression in the company	Leadership and career progression in public administration	Leadership and career progression in research	Prevention and action against gender-based violence	Methodologies applied to gender studies in the humanities and social sciences	n/a
UVSK SAV	Gender equality in science	Introduction to Gender Equality	Gender in research	Gender sensitive management	Empowerment	Sexual harassment on workplace	Gender sensitive language

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

FRCT	Gender equality at FRCT	Unconscious bias	The dimension gender in research	Work-life balance and organisational culture	How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment	Tools for an inclusive language	n/a
------	-------------------------	------------------	----------------------------------	--	---	---------------------------------	-----

The Table 4 below shows the training programme schedule, reporting on the planned delivery dates. As it can be seen, there are partners that have already delivered some training modules, as it is the case of UB, UVSK SAV and ULPGC. Nevertheless, some other partners will start deploying them in September/October 2022. The training programme is expected to be finished by the end of November 2022. Exact dates have been provided by those partners that have already set them. As for the rest of the institutions, they will be finalized as the organization of the event progresses.

Table 4. Schedule of the ATHENA training programmes

ATHENA institution	Module 1	Module 2	Module 3	Module 4	Module 5	Module 6
JSI	5 Oct 2022	13 Oct 2022	20 Oct 2022	27 Oct 2022	11 Nov 2022	
UJK	1/10/2022-30/11/2022	1/10/2022-30/11/2022	1/10/2022-30/11/2022	1/10/2022-30/11/2022	1/10/2022-30/11/2022	
UB	9 Jun 2022	Oct 2022	Jun 2022	Oct 2022	Oct 2022	
URAK	20 Sep 2022	27 Sep 2022	04 Oct 2022	11 Oct 2022	19 Oct 2022	
ULPGC	Nov 2022	Nov2022	Nov 2022	Nov 2022	24, 25, 26 May 2022 and 1 Jun 2022	
UVSK SAV	13 May 2022	23 May 2022	Sep 2022	9 Jun 2022	18 Mar 2022	28 Apr 2022
FRCT	19 Sep 2022	26 Sep 2022	3 Oct 2022	10 Oct2022	17 Oct 2022	

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Next subsections will report on the training outline from each ATHENA institution implementing the capacity building.

3.1 JSI training programme

Training outline
Training topic Gender equality at JSI
Rationale for the training <p>The Athena members and GEPI committee decided that the training on gender equality at JSI will be composed of 5 different modules, which will increase awareness and initiate discussion on this topic. We have considered all the focus groups at our institute (researchers, young researchers, middle and higher management, business and administration). We have tight collaboration with our external expert Prof Milica Antič Gaber, who also provided information on possible lecturers on specific topics as well helped prepare agenda for each module with regards to our needs at JSI. We have decided to prepare 5 modules on these specific topics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Unconscious bias2. Work-life balance and organizational culture3. Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making4. Gender equality in career progression and recruitment5. Ethics and integrity in research
Objectives of the training <p>The main objective of the training is to increase awareness on gender equality at our institute. As the institute covers the fields of natural sciences and technologies we do not have such type of education, training, or workshops and we are mostly not aware of gender equality or inequality at different levels. Thus, the main objective is to initiate discussion on these topics and to start thinking about gender equality at JSI, especially on the topics that are proposed.</p>
Overall objective <p>The overall objective of the training is to discuss and increase awareness of gender equality at JSI by organizing training composed of 5 different modules with topics that have been recognized as the most important for our institution. We will discuss the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making. Basic concepts on gender equality, diversity and gender bias in the academic field will be introduced and explained. This part is highly linked with gender equality in leadership and career progression and recruitment, which will compose a separate module and will address the key issues regarding a low number of women in the leadership positions and how to improve gender balance and what the benefits of mixed teams are. The work-life balance, which is currently</p>

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

a hot topic, will be another module also due to corona crisis and increased remote work. We will discuss how to improve work-life balance and which strategies can be used to detach from work when out of the office or in personal life. This module is relevant to increasing awareness of gender balance at the workplace and promoting gender equality at JSI. Another important topic is gender equality in career progression and recruitment, where issues with unconscious bias as well as how to recognize gender imbalance will be discussed. Good practices will be presented to increase awareness on this topic and to promote gender equality in recruitment and career progression at JSI. The last module will discuss the ethics and integrity in research and will also touch gender-based violence and sexual harassment. The objective of the module is to educate and inform the employees about the ethics and integrity in research – what the ethics and integrity codex represents, what it means, how a person should act like a respectable researcher and colleague in a professional environment (in context with ALLEA document (https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2018-Slovenian_dig.pdf)). The practical part of the module will additionally try to identify and address current problems with ethics and integrity among the employees of JSI.

Each module will be organised in such a manner that the first part will consist of a lecture on a specific topic which will be followed by the second part where round-table discussions or case studies will be organized to increase and promote collaboration and discussion of participants.

Specific objectives

The first module will focus on **unconscious bias**, which is a mandatory topic and is highly relevant also for our institute. The specific objectives will be to learn how to recognise practices of biased treatment of women and men in the academic field and to identify gender biases (conscious and unconscious) in the specific context of academic institutions. The important objective will also be to develop an understanding of how unconscious bias can affect our judgement and decision-making in specific situations.

In this part, we have confirmed the lecture from Prof Milica Antić Gaber on unconscious bias and a round table with guests from different companies and universities to discuss these questions.

In the second module we will focus on **work-life balance and organizational culture**, where two aspects of work-life balance will be presented: what the characteristics of the workplace that improves work-life balance are, and what employees can do in their personal time after work to properly detach from work.

To explore these, Prof Sara Tement from the Faculty of Arts, University of Maribor will be invited as a speaker. She is an occupational psychologist and an expert in

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

work-life balance: one of her recent projects deals with managing boundaries between work and personal life and its relationship with burnout. She will present general characteristics of work-life balance, how work-life interference can have negative effects on cardiovascular health, and how a successful psychological detachment from work can be achieved, using techniques from cognitive-behavioural therapy and mindfulness. She will also put some emphasis on the specifics of working from home, which proliferated during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the second part of the module, participants will work in groups and discuss aspects of their work that help them specifically in achieving a better work-life balance and brainstorming possible further improvements.

The third module will focus on **gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making**. This topic is recognised as an important one, as the number of women in leadership positions is actually decreasing and we have a low number of women in the decision-making bodies. The training will consist of the following parts. The introductory part where the data on the proportion of women at different leadership and decision-making positions in Slovenia and at Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI) will be presented, followed by the survey of the proportion of women in leadership positions at JSI in the last 30 years. The lecture will cover the theoretical background, i.e. the main concepts and concerns regarding gender equality in leadership positions and propose measures to improve the situation. Mirjana Dimic Perko with her board managerial experience and strong financial background will present the importance of mixed teams and show statistics on how companies with a more uniform structure of women and men in the leadership positions and in decision-making bodies are more successful. The interactive part will be a round-table discussion. Both female and male representatives on leadership positions in different segments of society including research will be asked to present their views on gender equality in leadership positions and measures to improve gender balance in leading positions.

The fourth module will deal with **gender equality in career progression and recruitment**. This module is also highly relevant for JSI, as we currently do not have the human resources (HR) unit that would deal with career progression and recruitment, instead, currently heads of departments are mainly responsible for this part. We will invite lecturers from different companies and research organisations to present their good practices and organize a round table to open the discussion. A well-recognized Slovenian research-oriented company Cosylab will present their gender equality plan with a focus on recruitment and establishing support for engineers in science. In this part also, a certification of the company as a socially responsible company (DOD certificate) will be presented and discussed.

In the fifth module we will focus on **ethics and integrity in research**, as this topic was chosen by our GEPI committee as well as by Athena members. This topic is important for our research institute as we have only recently accepted the codex of

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

ethics and integrity in research. The respective topic should be promoted and discussed among the employees to increase awareness. In this part, we plan also to discuss gender-based violence and sexual harassment which is one of the topics that should also be discussed at JSI.

Modality

Hybrid event in case of restrictions online

Format

Traditional lectures, workshops, round tables.

Language

Slovenian

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 2 h per module; 5 modules x 2 h = 10 h training

Period in which the training programme will take place: 5.10.2022- 11.11.2022

Duration of module 1: 2 h

Duration of module 2: 2 h

Duration of module 3: 2 h

Duration of module 4: 2 h

Duration of module 5: 2 h

Content

Module 1: Unconscious bias (mandatory topic addressing the staff and decision-makers)

- 1.) Examine the arguments that support the value of gender equality and diversity in RPOs.
- 2.) Outline the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making.
- 3.) Explore examples and case studies of unconscious bias.

Module 2: Work-life balance and organizational culture

- 1.) Understand the relations between gender equality, organizational culture in research and academic environments and work-life balance.
- 2.) Learn and discuss about inspiring practices for possible interventions and policies.

Module 3: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making

- 1.) Understand the main concepts and concerns regarding gender equality in leadership positions
- 2.) Understand the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making
- 3.) Become familiar with tools to improve institutional gender balance in leadership positions and decision-making
- 4.) Learn about successful implemented measures to improve gender balance

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

on leading positions

Module 4: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment

- 1.) Learning about positive practices to overcome inequalities in recruitment and promotion
- 2.) Understand and recognize the existing gender imbalances and bias in research organizations in career progression and recruitment
- 3.) Learning from best practices from top Slovenian companies

Module 5: Ethics and integrity in research

- 1.) Learning about ethic and integrity in research
- 2.) Understand the importance of ethical codex and how to act as a respectable researcher and coworker in a professional environment
- 3.) Gender based violence and sexual harassment
- 4.) Understand and recognize existing problems – round table discussion with examples.

Material

PPT presentation

Tools and techniques to be used

Round table discussions and workshops to generate active participation

Agenda

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

The training programme will consist of 5 modules, each module will include first a short presentation of the ATHENA project and related activities at JSI. Furthermore, statistical data where relevant and proposed improvements to overcome specific problems will be presented. After the introductory part, the lecture on a selected topic will be given by different external collaborators (approximately 1h). After the lecture, the round table or workshop will be organized for an additional 1h. The first training will start on 5.10.2022 with the topic of unconscious bias. The other trainings will follow, so far, they are planned for the 13th, 20th and 27th October, and 11th November. The trainings will be organized in the JSI lecture room in hybrid form.

It is planned to have the following agenda:

5. 10. 2022, 10.00 - 12.00: Unconscious bias, coordinator: Alma Mehle.

13. 10. 2022, 10.00 - 12.00: Work-life balance and organizational culture, coordinators: Junoš Lukan, Dr. Vida Vukašinić.

20. 10. 2022, 10.00 - 12.00: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making, coordinator: Prof. Barbara Malič, Prof. Miha Čekada.

27. 10. 2022, 10.00 - 12.00: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment, coordinators: Vesna Butinar, Prof. Spomenka Kobe.

11. 11. 2022, 10.00 - 12.00: Ethics and integrity in research, coordinators: Pia Starič, Assist. Prof. Ita Junkar.

3.2 UJK training programme

Training outline

Training topic

Equal opportunities in science and research

Rationale for the training

The need to organize trainings in field of Gender Equality awareness-raising for staff and students at Jan Kochanowski University was diagnosed during the research process and underlined in the Gender Equality Report for the Jan Kochanowski University of Kielce (D2.3.). One of the important aspects (Recommendation # 1) of changing disproportions and ensuring equality in all areas at the university, should ensure the active education policy in the field of equality, tolerance, prejudice, discrimination and raising awareness on gender (in)equalities issues by access to information, trainings, conferences. Awareness efforts should target students as well as UJK employees in all departments and

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

academic disciplines, regardless of age, grade, or gender. That is why the training program covers different modules addressed to different target groups and challenges aiming the GE awareness-raising at JKU. Trainings will be available on the unit website for all interested students, Ph.D. students, academics, researchers, management, and administrative staff.

Objectives of the training

Overall objective:

Supporting the process of institutional change, aimed at addressing gender unbalances in recruitment, retention, career progression of researchers, and decision-making positions, and integrating a gender dimension in research content by raising awareness of the whole institution towards gender equality.

Specific objectives:

1. Outline the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making.
2. Make researchers more sensitive towards the gender dimension of/in science
3. Proper counteract discrimination in projects,
4. Promote initiatives to support the career progression of the underrepresented gender in high and top positions
5. Use inclusive language in broadly understood university communication.

Modality: online (webinar)

Format: the first modules will be online (live webinar) by the MsTeams platform, they will be recorded and later the course of study will be uploaded on the institution's website with additional materials to download and self-study. The number of downloads will be monitored.

Language: Polish

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 10 hours

Period in which the training programme will take place: 01.10-30.11.2022

Duration of module 1: 2 hours

Duration of module 2: 2 hours

Duration of module 3: 2 hours

Duration of module 4: 2 hours

Duration of module 5: 2 hours

Content

Module 1: Unconscious bias in the workplace

Target group: decision-makers, administrative staff, academics, researchers,

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Ph.D. candidates, students

The content of the module will include general information about human affection by bias, and answer the question of how to eliminate prejudice in the organisation and create a fair and inclusive working environment.

- 1.) The relationship between bias, prejudice, and discrimination
- 2.) Different types of workplace biases.
- 3.) Unconscious bias and its impact on the workplace and working relationships
- 4.) How to recognize, understand and manage hidden biases
- 5.) Methods for reducing or eliminating bias from the decision-making process
- 6.) Good practices

Module 2: The gender dimension in research - including gender issues in research

Target group: academics, researchers, Ph.D. school, students

The content of the module will include both theoretical to help researchers to understand the “gender and science” issue and make them more sensitive towards the gender dimension of/in science, and practical cases of creating a common knowledge base and a shared vocabulary on gender equality in research. The module covers topics:

- 1.) Gender-blind research, gender-sensitive research, gender-specific research – differences
- 2.) How the gender dimension of research content contributes to excellence in research?
- 3.) How to integrate the gender dimension into research content in all research areas?
- 4.) Case studies based on concrete examples drawn from specific research fields: ex. management, history, medicine, engineering.

Module 3: Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in research projects - universal project framework design

Target group: academics, researchers, Ph.D. school, students, administrative staff (project management departments)

The goal of the training is to prepare staff, students, and doctoral students to properly counteract discrimination in projects, which is not only based on the abandonment of discrimination. Training will show them how to care for equal opportunities which mean active work and planning solutions that contribute to reducing the barriers experienced by various social groups in free access to

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

goods, services, information, and infrastructure. Topic:

- 1.) Principle of equal opportunities and non-discrimination including accessibility for people with disabilities - formal requirements for regional, national, and international projects,
- 2.) Horizontal and vertical approaches in defining equal opportunities in projects,
- 3.) Gender neutrality principles of the project,
- 4.) Principles of product (output, outcome) neutrality
- 5.) Creation of a gender-balanced research team.

Module 4: Equality in career progression and recruitment

Target group: management, academics, researchers, Ph.D. school, students, administrative staff

The content of the training will include both theoretical issues of how to promote gender-inclusive and bias-free recruitment, career progression, retention and evaluation policy in the institution and practical cases of “good practices” in this area. The module includes:

- 1.) The gender-aware internal recruitment and evaluation system – how it should work?
- 2.) Initiatives to support the career progression of the underrepresented gender in science, research career but also high and top positions – what staff can do?
- 3.) Good practices, tools, and methods particularly dedicated to the underrepresented gender (ex. mentoring initiatives for a newly hired faculty member, coaching, letters of recommendations, empowerment courses to improve visibility, self-confidence, negotiating and leadership skills) – how it works in other organizations?

Module 5: Inclusive language

Target group: decision-makers, management, administrative staff, academics, researchers, Ph.D. school, students

The content of the training will include both theoretical issues of discrimination, equal treatment, diversity, and the practical dimension of inclusive language and a proposition to use inclusive forms in speech and writing. Participants will know better what the use of gender-inclusive language means? The module includes:

- 1.) Exclusive and inclusive communication,
- 2.) How to talk and write to and about people/groups at risk of discrimination,
- 3.) Straightsplaining, mansplaining, victimization.
- 4.) The principles for gender-inclusive communication in formal and informal oral and written texts

5.) Examples.

Material

As part of the training program, a powerpoint presentation will be developed and used for each training module, made available for users to download from the website in a pdf version after the training. The presentation will present both text and graphic material, examples of good practice.

There will also be available audio-video material (recording of 2 hours of training, .av format), which participants, people interested in training will be able to play at any time and study by themselves.

Tools and techniques to be used

The training is planned online (webinar), lecture, storytelling, good practices analysis, and examples. In materials there will be some exercises, questions and answers fields.

Agenda

Timing	Content/module	Trainer
5 min	<p>Intro</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the training program. • Information about learning objectives, content of training modules, working techniques, availability of materials and cofinancing (repeated before each module) 	The Gender Equality Ombudsman
2 h	<p>Unconscious bias in the workplace</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding Bias • Recognizing Bias • Addressing Bias • Good practices 	External Expert
2 h	<p>The gender dimension in research - including gender issues at research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender-blind research • Gender-sensitive research • Gender specific research • Good practices 	External Expert
2 h	<p>Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in projects - universal project framework design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizontal approach in defining equal opportunities in projects, • Vertical approach in defining equal 	External Expert

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

	<p>opportunities in projects,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a gender-balanced research team, • Good practices 	
2 h	<p><i>Equality in career progression and recruitment</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal recruitment and evaluation system elements • Career progression support Initiatives • Good practices 	External Expert
2 h	<p><i>Inclusive language</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusive and inclusive communication, • Straightsplaining, mansplaining, victimization. • The principles for gender-inclusive communication in formal and informal oral and written texts • Examples 	External Expert

3.3 UB training programme

Training outline
<p>Training topic</p> <p>A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases</p>
<p>Rationale for the training</p> <p>This training module builds on the research findings and on the recommendations provided in the Gender Equality Report for University of Bucharest (Deliverable D.2.3) carried out through the ATHENA project.</p> <p>One of the main findings of the research exercise is that overall, most stakeholders surveyed in the University of Bucharest (teaching and research staff, administrative staff, HR professionals, students) hold little information and disparate knowledge on gender equality. Respondents still hold many misconceptions regarding gender equality, have had little exposure to unconscious bias trainings and generally navigate with difficulty basic concepts and ideas related to gender equality in an academic setting. The Gender Equality Report highlights under Recommendation No.4 the need for a systematic and group specific tailored trainings on gender equality. The same recommendation suggests that informal, experiential and adult friendly methodologies should be used in order to enhance gender sensitivity and raise the level of gender awareness among various university stakeholders.</p> <p>In April 2020, the University of Bucharest adopted a 2-year Gender Equality Plan that encompasses trainings for increasing the level of gender awareness of</p>

several target groups (HR and administrative staff, researchers and teaching staff and students). These measures can be found under three of the eight priority areas of the Gender Equality Plan.

Objectives of the training

Overall objective:

- Examine the arguments that support the value of gender equality and diversity in RPOs/RFOs.
- Outline the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making.
 - Explore examples and case studies of unconscious bias.

Specific objectives:

Module 1: A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases in the University Administration

Specific Objectives:

- Increase awareness of basic gender equality concepts and principles in an academic setting
- Understand, recognize, tackle unconscious bias
- Identify and counter gender stereotypes
- Learn about the priority areas and targeted measures of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Module 2: A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases

Specific Objectives:

- Increase awareness of basic gender equality concepts and principles in an academic setting
- Understand, recognize, tackle unconscious bias
- Identify and counter gender stereotypes
- Learn about the priority areas and targeted measures of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Module 3: A Gender Equal University: useful concepts for students

Specific Objectives:

- Increase awareness of basic gender equality concepts and principles in an academic setting
- Understand, recognize, tackle unconscious bias

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

- Identify and counter gender stereotypes
- Learn about the priority areas and targeted measures of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Module 4: Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act

Specific Objectives:

- Increase awareness of gender based violence
- Explore various forms of gender based violence that can impact students or staff
- Look at examples of student led actions, campaigns and projects to tackle gender based violence in the university
- Learn about the priority areas and targeted measures of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Module 5: Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research

Specific Objectives:

- Increase awareness of gender focused research
- Present gender mainstreaming method
- Explore the added value of mainstreaming gender in research designs
- Look at examples of exemplary research that used gender mainstreaming as part of its methodology
- Learn about the priority areas and targeted measures of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Modality: Face to face and online (preference for face to face but online webinars could be organized if a new surge in Covid-19 cases will take place over the autumn of 2022)

Format: face to face, trainings webinars, online trainings

Language: Romanian

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 12

Period in which the training programme will take place: June – November 2022

Duration of module 1: 4 hours

Duration of module 2: 2 hours

Duration of module 3: 2 hours

Duration of module 4: 2 hours

Duration of module 5: 2 hours

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Content of the training modules

Module 1: A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases in the University Administration

1. Gender in the Academic Setting – Facts and Figures from EU and Ro
2. Unconscious Bias – what it is and how it influences decisions
3. Countering Gender Stereotypes
4. Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest a useful tool for UB Administration

Module 2: A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases

1. Teaching and Gender – Facts and Figures
2. Unconscious bias and teaching materials – examples from secondary school text books
3. Teaching with out of the box examples and bibliographies
4. Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest a useful tool for UB teaching staff

Module 3: A Gender Equal University: Useful Concepts for Students

1. Gender Equality and Higher Education Graduates: Facts and Figures
2. Gender stereotypes – what they are and how they influence students
3. Playing the Gender Equality Game (interactive part using a gender equality card game)

Module 4: Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act

1. Gender based violence – facts and figures
2. Main types of gender based violence in the University
3. Examples of youth led campaigns against gender based violence

Module 5: Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research

1. Gender and Inter-Disciplinary research – examples
2. Gender mainstreaming
3. How to added a gender angle to your research proposal
4. Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest a useful tool for researchers

Materials

- Develop a PPT presentation for each training
- Use existing info-graphics (also from the Gender Equality Report) to illustrate examples
- Use a feminist card game developed by a Romanian NGO to talk about gender stereotypes
- Develop a user friendly excerpt from University of Bucharest's Gender Equality Plan
- Short glossary of gender equality terms

Tools and techniques to be used

- Gender Stereotype Card Game

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

- Interactive group discussions
- Presentation
- Case studies

Agenda

Tentative Agenda

Module 1 A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases in the University Administration

Expected delivery month - June 2022

Expected delivery method: face to face training of 4 hours

Module 2 A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases

Expected delivery month - October 2022

Expected delivery method: face to face training of 2 hours

Module 3: A Gender Equal University: Useful Concepts for Students

Expected delivery month - June 2022

Expected delivery method: face to face training of 2 hours

Module 4: Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act

Expected delivery month - October 2022

Expected delivery method: face to face training of 2 hours

Module 5: Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research

Expected delivery month - October 2022

Expected delivery method: face to face training of 2 hours

3.4 ULPGC training programme

Training outline

Training topic

Advancing towards gender equality at the ULPGC

Modules topics:

Topic 1: Gender equality in leadership and decision - making positions

Topic 2: Gender equality in career progression

Topic 3: Reconciliation of work, family life and organizational culture

Topic 4: Gender- based violence

Topic 5: The gender dimension in research

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Rationale for the training

This activity is part of the commitment of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria to promoting the value of equality through training that emphasizes some of the issues that, for various reasons, are considered a priority in our institution, such as the gender perspective in teaching and research, female empowerment, the promotion of women in the professional career, the reconciliation of personal and family life, and gender violence.

In addition to the above, the choice of these topics has been motivated by the intention of completing the training offer of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria on these issues; as well as for the interest that both the students and the administration and services staff, and teaching and research staff have expressed through the surveys carried out.

Objectives of the training

Overall objective:

The general objective of the training is to raise awareness and promote the value of equality in the university community through the different programmed modules:

The general objective of modules 1, 2 and 3 is to make the university community aware of the ULPGC on the role of women as leaders in the three contexts of public administration, business and research and understand the role of gender bias in leadership and decision-making. It will also address, the problem of work-life balance that women usually face alone will be addressed, with the aim of analysing how this can influence their professional development and what measures can be effective to achieve greater co-responsibility.

The general objective of module 4 is to make the university community aware of the importance of prevention and action against gender violence.

The general objective of module 5 is to provide teaching staff and research staff in the social sciences and humanities with basic skills in qualitative methodologies applied to gender studies.

Specific objectives:

Specific objective module 1

- To examine the evidence on gender bias in leading companies in Europe, Spain and the Canary Islands and propose new actions to mitigate the problem.
- Familiarisation with tools to improve the institutional gender balance in leadership and decision-making positions. Special reference to reconciling work and family life.

Specific objective module 2

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

- To examine the evidence on gender bias in public administration management positions in Europe, Spain and the Canary Islands and propose new actions to mitigate the problem
- To learn about successfully implemented to improve the gender balance in leadership positions in public administration.

Specific objective module 3

- Examine the evidence on gender bias in leading research in Europe, Spain and the Canary Islands and propose new actions to mitigate the problem
- To understand the main concepts and concerns about gender equality in leadership positions, as well as to analyse the particular work-life balance issues, faced by women in leadership positions.

Specific objective module 4

- Promote a culture of prevention against gender – based violence.
- To provide students with information and basic concepts about gender roles or stereotypes that allow them to identify sexist behavior and combat the myths that commonly exist in cases of gender-based violence.
- To analyse legislation, procedures, actions and instruments to prevent, detect and combat gender-based violence.

Specific objective module 5

- Know and value feminist social studies and the gender perspective.
- To go deeper into the sources and methodological use, analyzing perspectives, methodologies, as well as the differences between techniques and their shortcomings.
- Explain the most appropriate qualitative methodologies and apply them with examples and case studies: field work, oral interviews and images.

Mode

Modules 1,2,3 and 4: Classroom-based

Module 5: Mixed modality (face-to-face and online)

Format

Modules: 1, 2, 3: parallel discussion workshops and traditional conference session.

Modules: 4 and 5: theoretical presentations and practical activities.

Language

Spanish

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 42 hours and 45 minutes

Period in which the training program will take place: from May 24 to November 11

Duration of module 1: 5h and 15 min

Duration of module 2: 5h and 15 min

Duration of module 3: 5h and 15 min

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Duration of module 4: 2h

Duration of module 5: 25h (synchronous / asynchronous sessions)

Content

Module 1: Leadership and career progression in the company

1. Framework presentation: "Inequality in the development of women's careers" (carried out simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Leadership styles in the company
3. Experiences in women's leadership
4. Proposals for progress
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals .

Preferred target group: university students, although other members of the university community may attend, as long as seating capacity permits.

Module 2: Leadership and career progression in public administration

1. Framework presentation: "Inequality in the development of women's careers" (carried out simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Leadership styles in public administration
3. Experiences in women's leadership
4. Proposals for progress
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals.

Preferred target group: university students, although other members of the university community may attend, as long as seating capacity permits.

Module 3: Leadership and career progression in research

1. Framework presentation: "Inequality in the development of women's careers" (carried out simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Leadership styles in research
3. Experiences in women's leadership
4. Proposals for progress
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals.

Preferred target group: university students, although other members of the university community may attend, as long as seating capacity permits.

Module 4: Prevention and action against gender-based violence

1. Identification of myths and stereotypes in gender violence
2. To Know the Spanish legislative framework on gender violence and its practical application
3. The different forms of violence against women and their impact.

Preferred target group: law students, without prejudice to the possibility of other university students attending, as long as capacity permits.

Module 5: Methodologies applied to gender studies in the humanities and social sciences

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

1. Origins and development of feminist social studies and the gender approach
2. How to make women visible: methodologies and techniques
3. Theoretical explanation of the methodologies studied and development of practical examples by the attendees.

Group objective: Teaching and research staff and research staff in general.

Material

Pending confirmation with the people who will participate in the different modules.

Tools and techniques to be used

Pending confirmation with the people who will participate in the different modules.

Agenda

May:

Module 5 "Methodologies applied to gender studies in humanities and social sciences"

Date: May 24,25,26, and June 1.

Total module time: 25h

November:

Module 4: "Prevention of and action against gender-based violence"

Date: November 3

Total module time: 2h

Module 1: "Leadership and career progression in the company"

Date: November 11

Total module time: 5h and 15min

Module 2: "Leadership and career progression in public administration"

Date: November 11

Total module time: 5h and 15min

Module 3: "Leadership and career progression in research"

Date: November 11

Total module time: 5h and 15 min

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

3.5 UVSK SAV training programme

Training outline
Training topic Gender Equality in Science
Rationale for the training During the gender audit, we have identified that in general, people are not aware about the gender issues, they are not able to reflect gender inequalities, because they lack of information. Therefore, the training consists of 6 modules in order to reflect the variety of experience and needs on the topic. The first module is the introductory, aimed for those who are curious and would like to learn more. Other modules are more target – through the issue (e.g. Module 2 on sex and gender dimension in research, Module 5 on gender sensitive language and Module 5 on gender based violence and harassment) or target groups (Modul 3 focusing on management and Modul 4 on young (but only) female scientists to support empowerment).
Objectives of the training Overall objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Increase overall awareness on the topic of gender, gender equality.• Increase the ability to reflect gender within research.• Increase the ability to reflect gender within management.• Inform about and support the individual and collective strategies to combat gender inequalities.• Increase awareness on Gender Equality Plan at the SAS.• Support the use of gender sensitive language within the SAS institutions and public relations.• Support management in addressing gender base violence and sexual harassment at the workplace (preventive and intervention focus).
Modality: online and offline Format: Lectures, webinar and discussion Language: Slovak
Structure and proposed duration of the training Total duration of the training programme: 19 Period in which the training programme will take place: March - October Duration of module 1: 3 hours + break Duration of module 2: 3 hours + break

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Duration of module 3: 3 hours + break

Duration of module 4: 3 hours + break

Duration of module 5: 4 hours

Duration of module 6: 3 hours

Content

Module 1: Introduction to Gender Equality

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Gender bias
- 3.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 4.) Individual strategies to address gender inequalities
- 5.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in addressing gender inequalities

Target group: researchers and administrative staff (wider target)

Planned: 13.5. 10:00 - 13:00

Module 2: Gender in Research (not only in Horizon Europe)

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Gender bias
- 3.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 4.) Feminist reflection of science
- 5.) Sex and gender dimension in research
- 6.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in addressing gender inequalities

Target group: researchers, higher and middle management, project managers and project leaders

Planned: 23.5. 09:00 - 12:00 or 26.5. 09:00 - 12:00

Module 3: Gender sensitive management

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Best practice in management
- 3.) Trends in leadership
- 4.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in gender sensitive management

Target group: higher and middle management

Planned: September 2022

Module 4: Empowerment

- 1.) Challenges women face in science
- 2.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 3.) Sexism
- 4.) Strategies to empower

Target group: female researchers, management and administrative staff

9.6. 09:00 - 12:00

Module 5: Sexual harassment on workplace

- 1.) Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

- 2.) Discrimination at workplace
- 3.) Best-practice
- 4.) Psychological first-aid for the employees who were violated

Target group: higher and middle management

Realized: 18/03/2022

Module 6: Gender sensitive language

- 1.) Feminist perspectives on language
- 2.) Slovak language and its possibilities to use inclusive language
- 3.) Examples and dilemmas
- 4.) Gender Equality Plan of the SAS – discussing how language was applied

Target group: higher and middle management, members of GEPI committee and Committee for Equal Opportunities at the SAS, researchers specializing in language sciences

Realized: 28/04/2022

Material

- PPT presentation
- Recommendations
- Recommended study materials

Materials will be sent to the participants after the training delivery. The SAS does not have any existing mutual platform, where the study materials can be shared and the existing website does not allow this kind of dissemination.

Tools and techniques to be used

- Presentations of the theoretical background on gender and gender inequalities, together with examples of best-practices, videos and suggested tools to promote GE.
- A moderated discussion will be characterized as a safe space for participants so they may express their opinions freely.
- A Socratic method will be used during the discussion.

Agenda

Module 1: Introduction to Gender Equality

2 hours: Lecture

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Ľubica Rozborová and Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

Module 2: Gender in research

2 hours: Lecture

www.athenaequality.eu

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Ľubica Rozborová and Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

Module 3: Gender sensitive management

2 hours: Lecture

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Ľubica Rozborová and Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

Module 4: Empowerment

1 hour: Lecture

1 hour: Exercises to practice empowerment

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Ľubica Rozborová and Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

Module 5: Sexual harassment on workplace

3,5 hours: Lecture

(Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation, Discrimination at workplace, Best-practice, Psychological first-aid for the employees who were violated)

0,5 hour: Discussion: G&A

Trainer: Slávka Karkošková (invited expert), Róbert karul (GEPI member, member of the SAS Presidium)

Module 6: Gender sensitive language

1,5 hours: Lecture (theoretical basis for the gender inclusive language and summary of challenges)

Break

1,5: Discussion on selected issues and challenges related to the implementing of gender inclusive language at the SAS, discussion on possible solutions

Trainer: Jana Cviková (GEPI, internal gender expert), Lucia Molnár Satinská (researchers from the SAS), Róbert karul (GEPI member, member of the SAS Presidium)

3.6 URAK training programme

Training outline
Training topic
Sustainable equality of women and men in the science
Rationale for the training
The implementation of Gender equality plan (GEP) at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” (URAK), Bulgaria, depends on the adequate analyses on different factors to get a clear understanding from all employees of URAK how the GEP will give sustainable protection of the equal opportunities of women and men

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

in the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” for decades ahead. We have decided to prepare 5 modules on these specific topics:

1. Unconscious bias and gender-based violence.
2. Work-life balance and organizational culture.
3. Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making.
4. Gender equality in career progression and recruitment.
5. Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

Objectives of the training

The main objective of the training is to keep in a sustainable way the existing awareness by all employees of URAK about the equal opportunities of women and men at the university.

Overall objective

To discuss and give further support for the successful implementation of the ATHENA’s Gender equality plan in the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev”. Different attendees will be invited to participate the trainings to reach as much as possible different people.

Each module will be organized in way that the first half to be about a lecture on a specific topic and then to have an interactive discussion, which to help the attendees to give their further input for the sustainability of the GEP especially after the end of the ATHENA project.

Specific objectives

The specific objectives of the topic “Unconscious bias and gender-based violence” are: (1) to have a better understanding of the unconscious bias, gender-based violence, including sexual harassment and (2) to have a better understanding how the GEP of URAK faces this problem. Important attention will be given to employment process and the attestation process.

The specific objectives of the topic “Work-life balance and organizational culture” are: (1) to have a better understanding of the work-life-balance and the main requirements to the organizational culture and (2) to have a better understanding how the GEP of URAK faces this problem. Important attention will be given to the ensuring equal opportunities for women and men in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration.

The specific objectives of the topic “Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making” are: (1) to have a better understanding on the equal opportunities of women and men to be in leadership positions and participate the decision-making process and (2) to have a better understanding how the GEP of

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

URAK creates environment for a sustainable legislation in URAK about this topic. Important attention will be given to the national legal frame; the election procedures of URAK; main internal documents at URAK for different types of payment.

The specific objectives of the topic “Gender equality in career progression and recruitment” are: (1) to have a better understanding of the equality between women and men in career progression and recruitment and (2) to have a better understanding how the GEP of URAK contributes in a sustainable way to this topic. Important attention will be given to key national legal acts; internal procedures of URAK; the role of GEP to have the key documents in URAK to guarantee the equal opportunities between women and men for career progression and recruitment.

The specific objectives of the topic “Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content” are: (1) to have a better understanding how women and men have equal opportunities for research and teaching and (2) to have a better understanding how the GEP of URAK contributes in a sustainable way to this topic. Important attention will be given to ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University, especially prevention against violence, as violation of human rights; the role of GEP to keep in a sustainable way the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University.

Modality

Face-to-face or online (in case of restrictions)

Format

Traditional lectures and workshops.

Language

Bulgarian

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 2 h per module; 5 modules x2 h= 10 h training

Period in which the training programme will take place: 20.09.2022-30.10.2022

Duration of module 1: 2 h

Duration of module 2: 2 h

Duration of module 3: 2 h

Duration of module 4: 2 h

Duration of module 5: 2 h

Content

Module 1: *Unconscious bias and gender-based violence (mandatory topic addressing the staff and decision-makers)*

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

- *Introduction to “Unconscious bias”*: Understanding of “unconscious bias”. Understanding of “gender-based violence, including sexual harassment”.

- *Role of GEP at URAK to avoid unconscious bias, gender-based violence, including sexual harassment*: Good practices at employment process. Good practices at attestation process.

Module 2: Work-life balance and organizational culture

- *Understanding of “Work-life balance and organizational culture”*: Introduction to the “work-life-balance”. Main requirements to the organizational culture.

- *Ensuring equal opportunities for women and men in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration*: Main internal documents at URAK. The role of GEP for the work-life balance and organizational culture at URAK.

Module 3: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making

- *Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to be involved in decision-making jobs in the University*: Introduction to the national legal frame. Introduction to the election procedures of URAK.

- *Ensuring equal payments of women and men on decision-making jobs*: Main internal documents at URAK for different payments. The role of GEP for development of sustainable legislation in URAK about this topic.

Module 4: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment

- *Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to be recruited at the University*: Introduction to the national legal frame. Introduction to the internal procedures of URAK.

- *Ensuring the career progression of women and men at the University*: Main internal documents at URAK. The role of GEP for development of sustainable legislation in URAK about this topic.

Module 5: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

- *Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University*: Prevention against violence, as violation of human rights and form of discrimination gender based. Introduction to the internal procedures of URAK.

- *The role of GEP on the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University*: Main actions in GEP of URAK. Expected outcomes from GEP.

Material

PPT presentation, internal documents of URAK

Tools and techniques to be used

- A lecture room with multimedia (in case of face-to-face classes).
- Virtual room (in case of online classes)

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

Agenda

The training programme will consist of 5 modules and each of them will follow the next Agenda:

- 14:00 – 14:05 Official opening.
- 14:05 – 14:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.
- 14:15 – 15:00 A lecture about the topic.
- 15:00 – 15:45 Round table for next steps.
- 15:45 – 16:00 Discussion and official closure.

The trainings will be organized in the facilities of Ruse University “Angel Kanchev” on the next dates:

- Module 1 – 20.09.2022
- Module 2 – 27.09.2022
- Module 3 – 04.10.2022
- Module 4 – 11.10.2022
- Module 5 – 19.10.2022

A reserve of time is given to 30.10.2022 in case of negative overlap of some of the trainings with other activities.

The main trainers will be representatives of GEPI Committee of URAK, as well as other responsible persons at URAK.

3.7 FRCT training programme

Training outline

Training topic

Gender equality at FRCT

Training modules

1. Unconscious bias
2. The gender dimension in research
3. Work-life balance and organisational culture
4. How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment
5. Tools for an inclusive language

Rationale for the training

The analysis of the focus groups and questionnaires applied in the Regional Fund of Science and Technology (FRCT) revealed an opposition between masculine and feminine perspectives, with male domination manifested as the perpetuation of hierarchical relationships and the difficulty of achieving a satisfactory work-life

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

balance.

Objectives of the training

Overall objectives:

- To discuss the main arguments that support the value of gender equality and diversity in RPOs and RFOs, deconstructing unconscious bias.
- Underline the importance of gender dimension in research, deconstructing prejudices and highlighting challenges and achievements.
- Understand the relations between gender equality, organisational culture in research and work-life balance.
- Facilitate awareness and the acquisition of assessment and intervention skills in cases of gender-based violence and sexual harassment at work.
- Analyse language and adapt linguistic practices to the current historical and cultural circumstances in Portugal, as well as the current norms governing the promotion of gender equality.

Specific objectives:

- Understand “the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making” (Gender training programme. Guidelines).
- Explore the «categories of perception» theorized by the French philosopher and sociologist Pierre Bourdieu in his book *Masculine Domination*.
- Sensitize the participants to a consequent reflection on the principles of submission and domination in their historical, cultural and philosophical bias.
- Explore gender mainstreaming in research, namely in Portugal and in Europe.
- Analyse gender bias regarding women in research.
- “Examine how gender considerations are incorporated into research and the importance of these throughout the research process” (Gender training programme. Guidelines).
- Raise awareness about the importance of policies and good practices for work-life balance.
- Know the main international and national legal and political instruments on work-life balance.
- Understand the concepts of gender-based violence and sexual harassment in research institutions and the gender bias that exists within institutional cultures.
- Raise awareness about the importance of policies to fight gender-based violence.
- Learn about practices to improve policies to fight against sexual harassment

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

at work, with a focus on RPOs/RFOs.

- Know the main international and national legal and political instruments for equality between men and women.
- Reflect on misogynistic machismo strategies designed to interfere in women's power of speech, focusing on the concepts: maninterrupting, bropropriating and mansplaining.
- Acquire tools to apply inclusive language, either in a gender-neutral way or referring to both sexes.

Modality: face-to-face

Format: lectures, workshops and interactive methodologies

Language: Portuguese

Structure and proposed duration of the training

Total duration of the training programme: 15 hours

Period in which the training programme will take place: 19 September – 17 October

Duration of module 1: 3 hours

Duration of module 2: 3 hours

Duration of module 3: 3 hours

Duration of module 4: 3 hours

Duration of module 5: 3 hours

Content

Module 1: Unconscious bias

- 1.) Lusitanian genealogy of deconstruction: the Feminist Manifesto of Ana de Castro Osório.
- 2.) Pure and unattainable virility and dedicated femininity: natural laws “versus” social laws.
- 3.) A disquieting case study: the books of conduct that advocate female behaviour.

Module 2: The gender dimension in research

- 1.) European Union guidelines for gender mainstreaming in research (key documents). The case of Portugal.
- 2.) The traditional view associating science with men and the scope of women’s visibility in research and scientific innovation. Examples of good practices.
- 3.) Gender dimension in research and as a scientific topic itself. Examples of successful projects.

Module 3: Work-life balance and organisational culture

- 1.) Women in the male world of working and biological reproduction.
- 2.) Socially imposed Agoraphobia and the male and female professions.

- 3.) Key documents and good practices for work-life balance. Examples of successful policies and projects.

Module 4: How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment

- 1.) Gender bias and concepts of gender-based violence and sexual harassment in institutional cultures.
- 2.) Policies to fight gender-based violence.
- 3.) Practices to improve policies to fight against sexual harassment at work, with a focus on RPOs/RFOs.

Module 5: Tools for an inclusive language

- 1.) National and international legal-political instruments on gender equality.
- 2.) Language, symbolic representations and power.
- 3.) Tools for the application of inclusive language.

Materials

- PowerPoint presentations
- Infographics
- Videos
- Texts

Tools and techniques to be used

The training will be organized in two registers: theoretical, which will include content exposure, concepts, arguments, and theories; theoretical and practical, questioning, analysis, exploration of texts and their nuclear content, as well as practical exercises to consolidate learning.

The methodology will be interactive, centred on the trainees, favouring the development of skills in consulting relevant documentation, production of reasoned argumentation, a debate of ideas in small and large groups, favouring the construction of explanatory schemes of the issues addressed.

Agenda

Module 1: 19 September

Module 2: 26 September

Module 3: 03 October

Module 4: 10 October

Module 5: 17 October

athena

gender equality to unlock
research potential

4. Material of the Gender Training Programme

The material used by each ATHENA institution in their institutional gender trainings may be consulted at the project e-platform (www.gender-equality.eu). It has been created a dedicated site to share it publicly so it can be accessible to any other organization interested in implementing institutional gender trainings.

The material can be directly assessed by the following link: <https://gender-equality.eu/materials/>

Figure 1. How to access the material at the ATHENA e-platform shows a screenshot on how to access the training material through the project e-platform. Any interested person should follow the following steps:

1. Access the project e-platform via www.gender-equality.eu
2. Click on the 'Trainings' item at the menu bar on the top.
3. Once inside the 'Trainings' site, click on 'Resources for institutional gender trainings' that can be found under the main page slogan.

Figure 1. How to access the material at the ATHENA e-platform